

Policy Principles for Research Data Management

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Data should be FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.² However, data sharing is subject to conditions imposed by laws and regulations (such as the General Data Protection Regulation; GDPR), as well as data sovereignty considerations that we must take into account to protect the interests of the university and its researchers. We therefore distinguish between FAIR archiving (closed) and FAIR publishing (open). All data should be *archived* with full provenance in a closed archive (FAIR for the institute) and a selection of data suitable for publication should be *published* on an open platform (FAIR for the outside world).

The following describes the principles for archiving and publication, the three types of storage required (Figure 1), and the administrative and academic quality control measures required.

1 Policy principles

There are two guiding principles that underpin RDM policy: The archiving principle and the publication principle. These principles serve as starting points; there may be exceptions (see below).

The archiving principle: We strive to store all data in a closed archive, indefinitely, with full provenance description, FAIR for the institute only.

Full provenance consists of (1) documentation of where the data came from, how they were collected, by whom, for what reason, who was involved, and what methods and instruments were used and (2) a description of the steps taken to get from the original raw data to the processed data to the final results. The archive must be closed because the raw data and provenance description contain confidential information.

Justification of the archiving principle:

- *Duty of care*: Although ownership of research data is ill-defined (and controversial), the institution must have access to all data collected under its responsibility, as it is responsible for ensuring compliance with relevant laws and regulations governing the use and handling of the data.
- *Secure storage*: A secure and closed archive managed by the university ensures that data is protected from loss, unauthorised access and inappropriate use over the long term. This is particularly important for data that is privacy sensitive or should not be released for other reasons (e.g. intellectual property, prevention of dual use, resale).
- *Safety in the practice of working with data*: Once the raw and potentially sensitive data has been properly archived, it is possible to de-identify the data and work with pseudonymised data instead. This allows sensitive data to be removed from workspace storage.

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This policy note has also been included as Appendix 3 in 'Data sovereignty, data governance and digital sovereignty' of the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (www.lcrdm.nl): <https://zenodo.org/records/10837008>. The policy principles were originally drafted to apply to the management of the types of research data commonly used in the social sciences, humanities and medicine. Wider application of these principles to other disciplines, possibly with adaptation, seems possible.

² Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). Comment: The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, [160018]; <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

- *Prevention of data loss*: Should a researcher accidentally lose data or make irreversible changes; it is still possible to retrieve previous versions from the archive.
- *Transparency and traceability*: Archiving data with full provenance allows verification of data, processing and analysis steps, etc., where appropriate, thus enabling traceability. This can also have a positive feed-forward effect, encouraging good data practices.
- *Reusability*: If researchers want to continue working with the data at a later stage or in a new study, archiving it with full provenance makes it possible to retrieve and reuse the data. This allows for follow-up research with other analysis techniques or new research questions, and more.

The principle is that all data should be retained indefinitely, but there are of course limitations on the extent to which this is possible and considerations to be taken into account, such as:

- *Purpose limitations*: Personal data should only be archived for specific, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not be processed further in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.³
- *Privacy*: Under the GDPR, personal data can be archived for varying lengths of time, provided there is a clearly enforceable policy in place, the data is not archived for longer than necessary for the defined purposes, and participants have been informed. This in turn means that data that include personal data cannot be archived indefinitely, and its limitations are already defined within the informed consent letters, and privacy agreement.
- *Contractual agreements*: Archiving may be restricted by agreements with other parties regarding retention periods.
- *Information duty*: A researcher should not archive research data without informing participants that their personal data will be archived. An informed consent should provide for this.
- *Policies and guidelines*: Institutions from various research disciplines have their own guidelines on Research Data Management (RDM) and subsequent archiving practices. The rationale behind the retention period for personal data must be clearly defined to justify the retention period when an authority requests such information.
- *Cost-benefit consideration*: Archiving large amounts of data for an indefinite period can be very costly. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully consider the costs of archiving in relation to the benefits it provides.
- *Proportionality*: In general, the time, effort and measures to achieve the retention of all data, indefinitely and with full provenance, should be reasonable and not excessive.

The publication principle: We strive to publish as much data as possible, accessible via a publication platform, as early as possible, with full description of terms of use, FAIR for the world.

Early and extensive data sharing is in line with the principles of open science, which aim to promote the progress of science by enabling (interdisciplinary) collaboration, reuse, aggregation, meta-analysis, and more, while also reducing unnecessary duplication of research. Publishing data also enhances recognition, as it allows other researchers to reuse and cite original work, thereby increasing visibility and potentially leading to more citations, which are important measures of

³ In accordance with Article 89(1) (GDPR)

academic impact and influence. Additionally, data sharing promotes transparency, enabling peers to replicate analyses, validate findings, or identify potential errors, all of which support higher standards of scientific integrity and trust. Finally, as most research is publicly funded and research data may be considered a public good, one might even feel obliged to make such data publicly available.

However, the extent to which data can be shared unconditionally may be limited by legal and sovereignty issues. The considerations outlined for the archiving principle also apply to the publication principle. There are also additional considerations that need to be taken into account:

- *Copyright issues:* According to legal scholars, there is no ownership, intellectual property, or authorship of research data, so copyright cannot be regulated.
- *Conflicting regulations:* Institutional, national, and international regulations and directives may conflict.⁴
- *Privacy:* Data with personal information cannot be shared due to privacy requirements, ethical considerations, informed consent restrictions, and possible purpose restrictions.
- *Information duty:* A researcher may not share research data without informing participants that their personal data will be shared. Informed consent should provide for this.
- *Contractual agreements:* Publication may be prevented by agreements with other parties on embargo periods, retention periods, purpose limitations, dual use prohibitions, resale prohibitions.
- *Knowledge safety:* Researchers and institutions must consider the possibility of data being misused by other parties, particularly for dual-use applications (i.e., those that can be used for both civilian and military purposes).
- *Digital sovereignty:* The university holds the research data and should protect itself from commercial lock-in by preventing commercial services from harvesting its data and becoming dependent on commercial endeavours, thereby compromising its independence and research integrity and its public service mission.

2 Prerequisites

In order to work according to the principles mentioned above, researchers need specific infrastructure. This includes appropriate storage facilities and support for archiving and publishing research data. Additionally, to safeguard data sovereignty, access to research data must be regulated. This is particularly important because ownership of research data may not exist or be defined, but access can be regulated by the data holder. Data holders are the researchers themselves or, depending on the applicable (local) regulations, their supervisors or managers or employers, who are responsible for collecting, storing and managing the data sets, ensuring their integrity, security and compliance with relevant regulations and ethical standards.

The data holder should decide which data to share, with whom, and under which conditions. Data descriptions can be published on a publication platform, with a link to a contract with terms of use. Only if an interested user agrees to the terms of use will he or she get access to the data. The user can then either download the data or perform remote analysis on the data, getting the results but not the data itself. The University of Amsterdam and SURF are developing a Research Data Exchange

⁴ For example: General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Digital Services Act, Digital Markets Act, Data Governance Act, EU Directive on Open Data and the Re-Use of Public Sector Information, Text and Data Mining articles in the EU Directive on Copyright in the Digital Single Market.

(RDX) that regulates such access, including the automated recording of signed usage contracts, for auditing purposes.⁵

3 Types of storage

Three types of storage are required to enable researchers to comply with the archiving and publication principles (see Figure 1):

- Workspace storage is temporary (e.g., cloud storage, local storage, laptops, or desktops) and is used in the collection, processing and analysis of data for the duration of a research project. This storage is only accessible to researchers. The use of unapproved, non-EU cloud service storage is not permitted (digital sovereignty⁶).
- Secure, closed storage for long-term archiving of data packages. Data packages include full provenance descriptions and appropriate metadata for indexing and cataloguing purposes. The archive is a closed facility, inaccessible to researchers themselves, but the archived data must be FAIR for the institute so that access can still be granted if required. Data packages can only be retrieved with the permission of the faculty dean or institute director.
- Open access publication platforms for the publication of data descriptions. Data packages that are suitable for publication (i.e., those that do not contain sensitive data) should be deposited in a repository for an indefinite period of time and referenced on a publication platform (e.g., DANS, OSF, ODISSEI, Zenodo). Access to these data packages should be regulated by an RDX (Research Data Exchange), subject to terms of use.

Figure 1: Storage, archiving, and publication of data in separate locations.

Note: Temporary storage will be provided as WORKSPACE storage for data processing and analysis, for the duration of the research project. Immediately after data collection, and at any other appropriate time, the researcher will submit data packages for archiving. The ARCHIVE stores data packages with full provenance for an indefinite period of time, closed, accessible only after approval by the Dean. Data packages suitable for publication are submitted to the PUBLICATION PLATFORM, which holds data packages for an indefinite period, open, but subject to use conditions, regulated by the Data Research Exchange (RDX).

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8269272>

⁶ Digital sovereignty describes a party's right and ability to independently control its own digital data and systems. It includes control over all digital tools and services that are used in research, including data, software, hardware, and other digital assets.

During the research project, upon completion of (substantial parts of) data collection or processing, the researcher should compile a data package and submit it to the data steward for archiving. Such a data package includes the original raw data, any processed data, and a full description of the origin and processing. As data packages for archiving contain confidential information, all storage for archiving is closed, accessible only to a limited number of people, only after permission from the director or dean. Data suitable for publication are packaged together with a data description and a contract with terms of use in a 'publication package' and submitted to the data steward for review and archiving prior to publication.

4 Administrative and academic quality control

Universities are responsible for good research data management (RDM) and the necessary IT infrastructure, in accordance with legal and institutional guidelines. For this reason, it is not possible for researchers to archive their data themselves without the intervention of the data steward. Researchers should also be discouraged from self-publishing their data until quality and compliance checks have been carried out.

Data stewards should act as gatekeepers in the (closed) archiving and (regulated) publication of data. They must check, or have checked, that data packages comply with laws and regulations, institutional policies, informed consent and contractual agreements, the FAIR principles, the Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, that provenance descriptions are complete, that metadata are correct and complete, that terms of use are correct and complete, and that any licenses have been applied correctly. If data packages are not yet compliant, the data stewards can also assist researchers by helping them, or arranging for someone else to help them, to make them compliant.

Data stewards may not have the time or expertise to review all data packages for all of the above. To support data stewards, a referral system should be in place to provide easy access to legal counsel to review legal issues, ethics committee members to review informed consent, data scientists or experts with specific knowledge within research institutes to review provenance descriptions and compliance with FAIR principles, and librarians to review metadata and maintain a catalogue of archived and published data.

Processes should be automated as much as possible to ensure smooth checks, manageable workloads and timely responses. Shortcuts can be used for data sets that do not raise legal or security issues. For example, if data sets do not contain personal information, not all checks are relevant.